

1 **Nanoengineered 3D culture substrate enables superior persistence and polyclonal**
2 **engraftment of genetically engineered hematopoietic stem cells**

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35 **SUMMARY**

36 *Ex vivo* culture of hematopoietic stem and progenitor cells (HSPCs) is required for gene therapy
37 applications but inadvertently triggers detrimental cellular responses, potentially threatening clinical
38 success. In this study, we employ nichoids, biocompatible 3D culture substrates with cell-scale
39 resolution, to provide HSPCs with mechanical support during *ex vivo* manipulation. This innovative
40 3D system improves HSPC multi-lineage differentiation and engraftment capacity by leveraging
41 mechanobiological control over nuclear morphology, cytoskeleton organization, metabolism, and
42 DNA integrity. Notably, 3D culture enables efficient genetic engineering across multiple platforms,
43 including long-range gene editing, base- and prime-editing, and lentiviral-mediated gene addition.
44 Moreover, this scaffold increases the clonal output and persistence of genetically engineered cells
45 in xenotransplantation experiments, including a clinical protocol for lentiviral gene addition in Wiskott-
46 Aldrich Syndrome. Overall, we propose a transformative approach to enhance the efficacy and
47 safety of emerging and established hematopoietic stem cell-based gene therapy applications.

48 INTRODUCTION

49 Autologous hematopoietic stem and progenitor cell (HSPC)-based gene therapies (GTs) offer a
50 promising one-and-done treatment for multiple immune-hematologic and genetic diseases, including
51 cross-correction of non-hematopoietic cells in some non-hematological disorders¹⁻⁴. Genetic
52 engineering of HSPCs was first achieved through semi-randomly integrating viral vectors like
53 gamma-retroviruses and pseudotyped lentiviral vectors (LVs)⁵⁻⁸, while nowadays gene editing (GE)
54 platforms, such as CRISPR/Cas9 and base- and prime-editors⁹⁻¹¹, can induce targeted modifications
55 up to single-nucleotide precision. Yet, despite numerous successes in clinical trials and the market
56 approval of some of these therapies^{6-8,12-19}, considerable challenges prevent a broader adoption of
57 these living drugs, including reaching high engineering efficiency without compromising the
58 functionality of HSPCs, ensuring the highest predicted safety of the cell product, and managing the
59 extremely high R&D and manufacturing costs²⁰⁻²². From a biological standpoint, genetic engineering
60 triggers various adverse reactions, including the activation of the DNA damage response (DDR) and
61 the formation of potential genotoxic byproducts, like indels, chromosomal rearrangements, or
62 insertional mutagenesis²³⁻²⁸. Moreover, exposure to *ex vivo* culture further induces DNA damage
63 and oxidative stress, which rapidly reduce self-renewal potential, promote differentiation, and
64 potentially lead to the loss of the most primitive hematopoietic stem cells (HSCs), responsible for the
65 life-long supply of the entire hematopoietic compartment²⁹⁻³². Altogether, these detrimental
66 responses diminish the yield and quality of genetically engineered cells, delay hematopoietic
67 reconstitution, and shrink the clonal repertoire of repopulating stem cells^{3,22,28,33,34}, therefore raising
68 potential efficacy and safety concerns, highlighting the long-term risk of developing clonal
69 hematopoiesis and blood malignancies.

70 In current GT protocols, *ex vivo* culture is not only required for delivering the vector payload or
71 the editing reagents, but also, in some cases, to increase the number of transplantable cells. Thus,
72 alongside the development of more efficient and precise editing tools and enhancers^{25,34-36},
73 significant efforts are spent to advance culture conditions to ensure the maintenance, and potentially
74 the expansion, of HSCs *ex vivo*. These include fine-tuning the supporting cytokine combinations,
75 supplementing small molecules like nicotinamide riboside, UM171, ferroptosis inhibitors, and
76 introducing only chemically defined reagents to avoid batch-to-batch variability and diminish possible
77 contaminants^{31,37-42}. Yet, traditional 2D cultures are unlikely to fully recapitulate all the essential
78 supportive elements of the endogenous HSC niche. Indeed, although the HSPC mechanobiology
79 field is still relatively in its infancy, several studies have highlighted the critical role of 3D cues and
80 mechanical forces in HSC specification and maintenance under both physiological and *ex vivo*
81 conditions⁴³⁻⁴⁹. For this reason, engineered 3D culture systems represent an appealing strategy to
82 model the architecture of the native bone marrow (BM) niche and provide mechanical support to
83 HSCs during *ex vivo* manipulation.

84 Here, we implemented a biocompatible 3D culture system into multiple GT protocols, improving
85 the persistence and clonal output of engineered cells for more effective and safer therapeutic
86 applications.

87 **RESULTS**

88 **3D culture increases the functionality of HSPCs upon *ex vivo* manipulation**

89 To provide mechanical support to HSPCs during *ex vivo* culture, we tested nichoids⁵⁰, chemically
90 and structurally stable 3D substrates micro-fabricated with cell-scale resolution, featuring a
91 miniaturized architecture of 10-30×15 μm elementary units produced through two-photon
92 polymerization (Figure 1A). Specifically, we seeded cord blood (CB)-derived CD34+ human HSPCs
93 either on standard culture wells (2D) or nichoids (3D) immediately after thawing and collected them
94 after three or seven days for downstream analyses (Figure 1B). To retrieve HSPCs from the scaffold,
95 we optimized a detachment protocol using a citrate solution, which allowed us to recover 75% of the
96 cells seeded without affecting cell viability or HSPC ability to generate colonies in the standard
97 colony-forming unit cell (CFU-C) assay (Figure S1A-C, Table S1).

98 First, we found similar percentages of viable cells and phenotypically defined HSPC subsets
99 between the two different culture systems (Figure 1C, Figure S1D,E). However, when testing the
100 clonogenic potential of an equal number of cells, 3D culture significantly increased the output of
101 mixed colonies, the progeny of more primitive and multipotent cells⁵¹, as well as the erythroid fraction
102 in the first time point (Figure 1D). As nichoids are fabricated on glass supports that may affect HSPC
103 behavior *per se*, we then compared standard tissue plates or glass coverslips with 3D culture.
104 Although we found a similar increase in erythroid colonies between glass and 3D, we reported higher
105 mixed-colony output exclusively in the nichoid condition (Figure S1F). Additionally, the improved
106 colony output occurred only if HSPCs were seeded immediately on 3D post-thawing, and not after
107 one to two days of initial 2D culture (Figure S1G), highlighting the importance of 3D stimuli during
108 early *ex vivo* culture adaptation.

109 To gather some insights on the more primitive HSPC compartment, we FACS sorted HSC-
110 enriched single cells (defined as CD34+CD133+CD90+CD45RA-) on the third day of culture and
111 assessed their multi-lineage differentiation potential along the myeloid (My), erythroid (Ery),
112 megakaryocytic (Meg), and natural killer (NK) branches⁵² (Figure S1H). Although not statistically
113 significant, we found a tendency towards an increased number of different lineages present within
114 single cell-derived colonies from the 3D condition (Figure 1E). Moreover, nichoid pre-cultured cells
115 gave rise to colonies with higher cellularity (Figure 1F), supporting enhanced functionality of the stem
116 cell compartment upon 3D culture. In terms of lineage specification, by analyzing in detail the
117 composition of uni-lineage and multi-lineage colonies, we found an expansion of the Ery-only and
118 MyNK output in the 3D condition, with a proportional decrease in the fraction of My-only and EryMeg
119 colonies (Figure S1I,J).

120 We next transplanted equal numbers of 2D or 3D cultured HSPCs into immunodeficient mice to
121 assess their hematopoietic reconstitution potential. Importantly, we reported higher human
122 chimerism in the peripheral blood (PB) of mice injected with nichoid-cultured HSPCs (Figure 1G),
123 with superior engraftment across multiple hematopoietic organs, including the bone marrow (BM)

124 and spleen (SP) (Figure 1H,I). Additionally, PB analyses revealed higher fractions of myeloid and T
125 cells present in the 3D condition (Figure S1K,L), while we observed similar graft composition in the
126 BM and a modest increase in T cell output in the SP (Figure S1M,N). At last, we purified human
127 CD34+ cells from the BM of the mice and found a higher clonogenic output of nichoid pre-cultured
128 HSPCs upon further re-challenging in the CFU-C assay (Figure 1J).

129 Altogether, our findings demonstrate that nichoids significantly enhance HSPC functionality
130 compared to traditional 2D cultures, supporting a critical role of 3D cues in preserving stem cell
131 properties during *ex vivo* manipulation.

132

133 **3D culture rewires the transcriptional profile of HSPCs and preserves nuclear and** 134 **cytoskeleton organization**

135 To dissect the molecular changes dictated by nichoids, we performed transcriptional analysis on
136 CB-derived CD34+ cells cultured on 2D or 3D at two different time points. Surprisingly, nichoids
137 induced a profound reshaping of the transcriptional profile of HSPCs, with differential modulation of
138 5399 and 5255 genes on days 4 and 7, respectively (Figure S2A). When performing gene set
139 enrichment analysis (GSEA), we found upregulation of cellular pathways related to the extracellular
140 matrix (ECM), cell adhesion, and cytoskeleton organization in the 3D condition, with the latter
141 significantly modulated only at the later time point (Figure 2A, Table S2). Conversely, we reported
142 downregulation of genes belonging to DNA replication, cell division, transcription, protein synthesis
143 and degradation, and oxidative respiration, features associated with more primitive and dormant
144 stem cells^{32,53-55}, and DDR signaling and DNA repair (Figure 2A).

145 To narrow down our analysis, we focused on specific genes involved in cell adhesion, cytoskeletal
146 rearrangements and signaling, and other HSPC-related pathways (Figure 2B). Thus, we found
147 upregulation of multiple integrin subunits (*ITGA1*, *ITGA3*, *ITGA5*, and *ITGB1*), combined with
148 differential modulation of microfilament and microtubule remodelers (such as *CLF1*, *CAPG*, *VIL1*,
149 *STMN1*, and *CLIP1*), and upregulation of focal adhesion genes and GPCRs (such as *PTK2*, also
150 known as focal adhesion kinase 1, *PAK4*, *ROCK1*, and *GPRC5C*), indicating a crosstalk between
151 the 3D scaffold and HSPCs, conceivably through mechano-sensing. Intriguingly, we also reported
152 downregulation of *CDC42*, a small GTPase of the Rho-subfamily that regulates HSC aging and
153 rejuvenation⁵⁶. Moreover, we detected upregulations of genes of the Notch and Wnt signaling
154 pathways (such as *NOTCH3*, *CREBBP*, *FZD2*, and *WNT5A*), *HLF*, *SLC2A1* (Glut1), *EPAS1* (Hif2a),
155 *FOXO1* and *FOXO3*, Akt, Yap/Taz, and *PTPN21*, which are fundamental for HSC specification and
156 maintenance^{43,48,57-67}.

157 At this stage, we then characterized nichoid-cultured HSPCs through multiple experimental
158 analyses to validate these findings. First, we assessed cell proliferation through CellTrace dye
159 staining and found that, while HSPCs grown on nichoids from both the bulk CD34+ and the more
160 primitive CD34+CD133+CD90+ subsets showed similar proliferation kinetics to traditional 2D

161 conditions in the first 4 days of *ex vivo* culture, they cumulatively performed fewer rounds of cell
162 division on day 7, as supported by heightened dye retention (Figure 2C, Figure S2B,C). Moreover,
163 we reported reduced oxidative stress with decreased accumulation of reactive oxygen species
164 (ROS) and 8-oxo-2'-deoxyguanosine (8-oxo-dG) DNA lesions (Figure 2D,E). In addition, alkaline
165 comet assay revealed fewer DNA single- and double-strand breaks in the 3D condition (Figure 2F).
166 Accordingly, we found fewer foci of pRPA and γ H2AX, upstream mediators of DNA damage sensing
167 and DDR activation⁶⁸(Figure S2D). Interestingly, we also reported reduced activation of the p38
168 MAPK kinase, which we recently identified as a crucial orchestrator of HSPC dysfunction upon *ex*
169 *vivo* culture and proliferation stress³² (Figure 2G, Figure S2E). Of note, similar results were also
170 observed when working with non-cryopreserved HSPCs purified from fresh CB (Figure S2F-J).

171 We then analyzed HSPC morphology in the presence of nichoids. Strikingly, we reported that 3D
172 culture endowed *ex vivo* cultured cells with a small and spherical shape, whereas HSPCs grown on
173 2D were enlarged and flattened (Figure 2H). This observation was confirmed for single cells as well
174 as their nuclei by measuring physical parameters like the volume and squashing (defined as the ratio
175 between the long and short axis of each cell, where squashing values close to 1 reflect spherical
176 objects) (Figure 2I,J). When performing this analysis, we also found a distinct architecture of the
177 microtubule cytoskeleton. Specifically, 3D cultured HSPCs presented a defined tubulin organization,
178 either polarized or equally distributed on the outer layer of the cell, while the 2D condition displayed
179 multiple microtubule bundles spread across the entire cellular volume (Figure 2K). Thus, we
180 assigned a tubulin score to single HSPCs based on the intensity of the tubulin signal along the cell
181 diameter (1 for multiple bundles, 2 for symmetrical distribution underneath the plasma membrane,
182 and 3 for polarized cells) (Figure 2L), and reported a distinct architecture of the microtubule
183 cytoskeleton between the two conditions, with the majority of nichoid-cultured HSPCs with polarized
184 tubulin distribution (Figure 2M), likely resulting from the interactions with the scaffold or the exposure
185 to different mechanical forces between the two culture systems.

186 Finally, to investigate whether distinct 3D culture platforms may differentially regulate HSPC
187 responses, we tested two alternative 3D systems, including a spongostan scaffold and a collagen-
188 based spheroid model (Figure S3A), previously exploited in hematological cancers^{69,70}. To this aim,
189 we employed HSPCs from mobilized peripheral blood (mPB), an adult CD34+ cell source of clinical
190 relevance^{3,71}. Despite a minor decrease in cell viability in the two alternative systems (Figure S3B),
191 which did not significantly impact HSPC subset composition (Figure S3C), we found that all 3D
192 cultures influenced HSPC behavior, although the effects on cell proliferation, oxidative stress, DNA
193 damage, p-p38 activation, cytoskeleton organization, and clonogenic potential varied across
194 conditions (Figure S3D-J). Interestingly, only nichoids increased the output of mixed colonies,
195 suggesting that different culture systems may ultimately induce both convergent and distinct
196 biological responses.

197 Overall, nichoids induce a profound transcriptional rewiring of HSPCs, upregulating molecular
198 pathways related to cytoskeleton remodeling and adhesion, with a concomitant decrease in cell
199 proliferation, oxidative stress, and DNA damage accumulation. Mechanistically, nichoids prevent
200 HSPC deformation and squashing of conventional 2D culture, preserve nuclear morphology and
201 tubulin polarity, and potentially facilitate adaptation to *ex vivo* culture with consequent preservation
202 of stemness properties.

203

204 **3D culture allows efficient gene editing across multiple platforms and endows HDR-edited** 205 **HSPCs with superior long-term engraftment**

206 We then reasoned that nichoids could improve genetic engineering protocols for clinical
207 applications, which involve additional manipulation steps that directly affect HSPC functionality^{23,24}.
208 Thus, we seeded human CB- or mPB-derived CD34+ cells on 2D or 3D and performed long-range
209 GE according to our established Cas9/AAV6 protocol²⁴, to achieve homology-directed repair (HDR)-
210 mediated insertion of a GFP reporter within the *AAVS1* locus (Figure 3A). Of note, HSPCs from the
211 3D condition were seeded on 2D post-nucleofection for functional studies to avoid repetitive cycles
212 of detachment and reseeded, which could increase cellular stress and diminish the quantity of
213 available edited HSPCs.

214 Nichoid pre-culture did not affect the viability and the fractions of HSPC subsets, even if the GE
215 procedure was generally less tolerated in the mPB source (Figure S4A,B). Additionally, we reported
216 comparable editing efficiencies across culture conditions in both the bulk CD34+ and the more
217 primitive CD34+CD133+CD90+ fractions, although lower in mPB (Figure 3B, Figure S4C-E).
218 Intriguingly, nichoid pre-culture was sufficient to slow down HSPC proliferation even upon re-plating
219 on standard 2D culture (Figure S4F). Nonetheless, the fraction of cells in the HDR-permissive S/G2
220 cell cycle phases at the time of nucleofection was similar between culture conditions (Figure S4G),
221 thus explaining the comparable editing levels. Importantly, nichoids improved the mixed-colony
222 output of edited cells, with a slight increment also in the erythroid fraction (Figure 3C).

223 We then assessed the repopulating potential of edited HSPCs. To this aim, we exploited two
224 validated and transiently expressed editing enhancers, a dominant-negative p53 variant (GSE56) to
225 counteract GE-induced DDR activation and an adenoviral helper protein (Ad5-E4orf6/7) to favor
226 HDR engagement²⁴ (Figure 3A, Figure S4H-L). We found higher human chimerism in the PB, BM,
227 and SP of mice from the nichoid group (Figure 3D,E, Figure S5A), with comparable levels of HDR-
228 edited cells, assessed by both GFP expression and molecular analysis (Figure 3F, Figure S5B-E),
229 and graft composition (Figure S5F-H) between the two conditions. Moreover, nichoid pre-cultured
230 CD34+ cells recovered from the mice maintained a higher clonogenic potential (Figure 3G). At this
231 stage, we then specifically challenged long-term HSCs by injecting BM-derived CD34+ cells from
232 primary mice into secondary recipients. Strikingly, we reported higher engraftment in the 3D group
233 across all the hematopoietic organs (Figure 3H,I, Figure S5I), with a three- to six-fold increase in the

234 percentage of HDR-edited cells (Figure 3J,K, Figure S5J,K) and similar graft composition compared
235 to the 2D group (Figure S5L-N), confirming the beneficial effects of nichoid for preserving functional
236 stem cells upon genetic manipulation.

237 Finally, we observed similar *in vitro* results also when performing base- and prime-editing (BE
238 and PE, respectively) in mPB-derived HSPCs using optimized mRNAs encoding for an adenine base
239 editor (ABE8.20-m) or prime editor (PE3max)²⁵ to knock out (KO) the *B2M* gene (Figure 3L-N, Figure
240 S5O-U).

241 Collectively, nichoids enable efficient GE and enhance the functionality of edited HSPCs across
242 multiple platforms, including Cas9/AAV6, BE, and PE. Moreover, 3D culture improves the long-term
243 reconstitution of engineered HSPCs, increasing the persistence of HDR-edited cells through serial
244 transplantation.

245

246 **3D culture increases the clonal output of repopulating HSPCs upon lentiviral gene addition**

247 As most market-approved and in late-stage development HSPC-GTs rely on LV-mediated gene
248 addition, we tested whether nichoids could further advance these protocols. Upon a 24h *ex vivo* pre-
249 stimulation, we performed LV transduction of mPB-derived CD34+ cells in 2D or directly on nichoids,
250 in the presence of 16,16-dimethyl prostaglandin E2 (PGE2) alone^{15,37} or in combination with the
251 transduction-enhancer cyclosporine H (CsH)³⁵, to achieve LV-mediated insertion of a GFP reporter
252 (Figure 4A).

253 As expected, cell viability was not affected by CsH administration and was similar between the
254 two culture conditions (Figure S6A). Moreover, while we reported a comparable fraction of
255 transduced cells across subsets (Figure 4B, Figure S6B) and vector-copy number (VCN) (Figure
256 S6C) in 2D or 3D, CsH allowed reaching saturating levels of GFP+ cells even at lower LV multiplicity
257 of infection (MOI) (30 vs. 100). Notably, nichoids improved the erythroid and mixed colony-forming
258 potential of transduced cells, even in the presence of CsH, which did not affect HSPC clonogenic
259 output *per se* (Figure 4C).

260 To validate these findings, we transplanted cells transduced with CsH and found higher human
261 chimerism in the PB, BM, and SP from mice of the nichoid group (Figure 4D,E, Figure S6D). Of note,
262 almost the entire grafts were composed of GFP+ cells (Figure 4F, Figure S6E,F). Additionally, 3D
263 culture increased the T cell output in the PB of the mice (Figure S6G), while we observed a similar
264 composition to the 2D condition in the BM and SP (Figure S6H,I). Moreover, BM-derived CD34+
265 cells from the 3D group maintained a higher clonogenic potential when challenged in the CFU-C
266 assay (Figure 4G), indicating that even a brief period of *ex vivo* culture as short as 36h on nichoids
267 can benefit the functionality of HSPCs in long-term experiments.

268 To further characterize the efficacy and safety of 3D culture in LV-based GT approaches, we also
269 monitored the clonal dynamics of engrafting HSPCs through integration site (IS) analyses^{8,72}. We
270 retrieved a high number of unique integrations across the PB, BM, and BM-purified CD34+ cells of

271 both conditions, which were generally more abundant in the 3D group (Figure S6J). In line with the
272 relatively short half-life of most hematopoietic progenitors supporting the early engraftment phase,
273 we found only a moderate persistence of PB-repopulating clones over time, while we observed the
274 highest clonal sharing between the BM and BM-derived CD34+ HSPCs at the endpoint (Figure 4H,
275 Figure S6K). Importantly, no clonal expansion events were reported in any of the mice (Figure 4H,
276 Figure S6K). Focusing on the complexity of the clonal repertoire, we then estimated population size
277 and diversity by normalizing the number of unique integrations and the Shannon diversity index on
278 the VCN. Thus, we found a higher number of engrafting clones and improved clonal diversity in the
279 3D condition (Figure 4I,J), indicating that nichoids better preserved the fraction of HSPCs capable
280 of reconstituting the hematopoietic system. Finally, gene targeting frequency analyses confirmed no
281 preferential enrichment of common ISs (CIS) within oncogene or tumor suppressor loci (Figure 4K,
282 Figure S6L).

283 Altogether, our data extend the beneficial properties of nichoids beyond precise GE, with 3D
284 culture increasing the number and diversity of engrafting HSPC clones upon LV-mediated gene
285 addition.

286

287 **3D culture ameliorates the engraftment and clonal complexity of gene-corrected HSPCs in** 288 **Wiskott-Aldrich Syndrome**

289 Lastly, we aimed to confirm our findings in a clinically relevant setting, specifically in a genetic
290 disease with an already validated GT protocol. To this end, we obtained mPB-derived CD34+ cells
291 from two Wiskott-Aldrich Syndrome (WAS) patients and performed two rounds of LV transduction
292 according to the clinical protocol⁷³, transferring a functional copy of the Wiskott-Aldrich syndrome
293 protein (WASP) using GMP-compliant vectors and reagents. As in clinical manufacturing, HSPCs
294 were seeded in 2D upon coating with retronectin. Conversely, retronectin was not introduced in the
295 3D group to avoid interfering with cell retrieval from nichoids (Figure 5A).

296 While we found comparable cell viability and subsets composition (Figure S7A,B), the VCN was
297 lower in the nichoid group (Figure S7C). This was likely caused by the lack of retronectin, as
298 suggested by similar transduction experiments in HSPCs from healthy donors (Figure S7D).
299 Nevertheless, the mixed-colony output was higher in the 3D condition even in this diseased-
300 background setting (Figure 5B).

301 To further corroborate these data, we then performed xenotransplantation and found improved
302 engraftment in the PB of mice from the 3D group at the first time point (Figure 5C), suggesting that
303 nichoid culture may facilitate an earlier hematopoietic recovery of GT-treated patients. Moreover, we
304 observed higher human chimerism in the BM and the SP at the end of the experiment (Figure 5D,E),
305 with VCN reflecting the measurement of pre-infusion cells (Figure S7E). When looking at graft
306 composition, we reported a modest increase in myeloid cells in the PB and CD34+ cells in the BM
307 of the 3D condition, while the SP composition was comparable between groups (Figure S7F-H).

308 At last, we performed IS analyses to monitor the clonal dynamics of engrafting HSPCs and further
309 characterize the efficacy and safety of integrating nichoids into the gene addition workflow for WAS.
310 In line with the higher VCN, the presence of unique integrations was generally more abundant in the
311 2D group (Figure S7I). In addition, no clonal expansion was reported in any of the mice, with only a
312 moderate persistence of PB-repopulating clones over time (Figure 5F, Figure S7J). Yet, despite the
313 different transduction efficiencies, the estimated population size of engineered cells was comparable
314 between conditions (Figure 5G), with improved clonal diversity in the nichoid group (Figure 5H),
315 indicating a more desirable clonal profile for therapeutic scopes. Finally, none of the mice showed
316 preferential enrichment of CIS within oncogene or tumor suppressor loci (Figure 5I, Figure S7K),
317 consolidating the safety of this approach.

318 In summary, 3D culture enhances the repopulating capacity and clonal complexity of engineered
319 HSPCs from WAS patients, conceivably enabling more efficient and safer clinical applications.

320 **DISCUSSION**

321 Despite the constant optimization of *ex vivo* culture conditions, maintaining or potentially
322 expanding functional HSCs remains challenging⁷⁴. In this context, we reasoned that GT protocols
323 could benefit from the adoption of innovative 3D systems providing mechanical support to HSCs
324 during *ex vivo* manipulation. Consistent with the emerging concept of early-culture adaptation^{30,75},
325 seeding HSPCs on nichoids from the very beginning of the *ex vivo* culture profoundly rewires their
326 transcriptional profile, limiting the accumulation of DNA damage and influencing cellular metabolism,
327 reflecting features of slow cycling and more functional stem cells^{32,53–55}. Mechanistically, nichoids
328 prevent HSPC deformation typical of 2D cultures, preserving nuclear morphology and tubulin
329 polarity, which are closely tied with stem cell function. Indeed, squashing imposes mechanical stress
330 on nuclei, promoting chromatin remodeling, DDR activation, and premature exhaustion^{49,76–78}, and
331 HSPCs enlarge under stress conditions, including repeated cell divisions and aging⁷⁹. Likewise, loss
332 of tubulin polarity caused by the upregulation of the Rho GTPase *CDC42* drives epigenetic rewiring,
333 alterations of cell division, aging, and functional decline of HSCs^{56,80,81}. Therefore, nichoids may
334 prevent the accumulation of aging-like detrimental responses occurring in conventional 2D cultures,
335 presumably through the sole regulation of mechanical forces.

336 While pharmacological modulation of individual pathways is unlikely to recapitulate the complex
337 effects induced by 3D culture, future studies could explore dynamic cell cultures in stirred or perfused
338 bioreactors^{82,83}, which could further modulate cell mechanobiology. Besides, nichoids should be
339 compared with other 3D systems developed for human HSPCs but not yet tested for genetic
340 engineering^{84–88}. For instance, hydrogels and bioprinting offer a customizable solution to mimic the
341 biochemical properties of the ECM and generate more complex 3D structures using biomaterials
342 and living cells, providing tunable architectures that can be functionalized with bioactive molecules.
343 Conversely, nichoids are nanoengineered through two-photon polymerization, which enables higher
344 spatial resolution compared to traditional bioprinting techniques⁸⁹, and lack ECM functionalization to
345 avoid introducing potential degradable molecules, as well as facilitating cell retrieval from the
346 scaffold, which represents one of the critical limitations of current 3D approaches. Given the
347 multitude of fabrication techniques and customizable parameters, such as stiffness, porosity, and
348 biochemical cues, rapid advances in the field may allow future side-by-side comparisons to identify
349 optimal 3D conditions that faithfully recapitulate the physiological HSC microenvironment, further
350 improving HSPC-based therapies.

351 Beyond HSPC biology, our work shows that nichoids support efficient genetic engineering across
352 multiple GT settings, including Cas9/AAV6-, BE-, and PE-mediated gene editing and LV-mediated
353 gene addition. Most importantly, 3D culture enhances the engraftment and clonal output of edited
354 cells, potentially improving efficacy and safety by diminishing the risk of clonal hematopoiesis and
355 malignant transformation in patients^{3,22,33,34,90}. Additionally, we found a broad modulation of DNA
356 damage, DDR signaling, and DNA repair pathways in 3D, with no insertional mutagenesis and pre-

357 malignant clonal expansion. Whether nichoids affect other genotoxic events related to genetic
358 engineering, such as on/off-targets, indels, and chromosomal rearrangements, remains to be
359 elucidated^{26,91-93}. However, our results suggest that 3D culture may improve genome integrity by
360 limiting culture-associated DNA damage, endowing engineered HSPCs with enhanced safety
361 profiles.

362 Finally, while we validated our findings in Wiskott-Aldrich Syndrome, we anticipate that 3D culture
363 could particularly benefit BM-failure conditions, like Dyskeratosis Congenita and Fanconi anemia, in
364 which HSPCs are progressively lost during *ex vivo* manipulation^{94,95}. In addition, 3D culture may also
365 enhance HSPC expansion protocols for allogeneic transplantation^{74,96,97}. Besides, future studies may
366 further compare our approach with alternative therapeutic strategies, such as *in vivo* delivery of
367 editing reagents or cells directly embedded in 3D matrices^{98,99}. However, while conceptually exciting,
368 *in vivo* gene therapy for HSPCs is still in its early stages and currently faces several technical and
369 safety challenges, such as delivery modalities, limited targeting efficiency, off-target activity, and
370 difficulties in controlling dose and biodistribution. Similarly, translation of implantable 3D scaffolds
371 carrying engineered cells would require careful evaluation of several key aspects, including
372 achieving efficient genetic engineering either outside the scaffold or directly *in situ*, ensuring that
373 implantation does not inadvertently transfer residual reagents and viral particles into the patient, and
374 verifying long-term stability and biocompatibility post-implant.

375 In conclusion, our work establishes 3D culture as an innovative strategy to preserve the
376 functionality of HSCs during *ex vivo* manipulation for multiple clinical scopes, laying the foundation
377 for enabling more effective and safer gene and cell therapies.

378 **LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY**

379 Here, we demonstrated the potential of 3D culture in small-scale preclinical testing across multiple
380 relevant contexts. However, direct *in vivo* validation of every possible combination of HSPC source
381 and genetic engineering strategy will be necessary to confirm these findings within each specific
382 application. Additionally, our xenotransplantation experiments were performed by injection of
383 matching numbers of HSPCs, although different settings, including limiting-dilution and injection of
384 the total outgrowths of the same starting HSPC number (t_0 equivalent), would allow further dissection
385 of the biological benefits of 3D culture and technical differences related to cell recovery from the
386 scaffolds. Finally, nichoids will require additional refinements and optimization to support production
387 scale-up and incorporation into GMP-compliant systems for clinical applications. Specifically, large-
388 scale production would require *ad hoc* investments to speed up manufacturing and meet clinical
389 demands. Moreover, the current design of nichoids, fabricated on a glass support, may limit their
390 immediate integration into cell expansion bags usually employed in clinical workflows. However, we
391 envision that nichoids could fit inside custom-designed bioreactors, which may also further facilitate
392 cell retrieval.

393 **RESOURCE AVAILABILITY**

394 **Lead contact**

395 Further information and requests should be directed to and will be fulfilled by Raffaella Di Micco
396 (dimicco.raffaella@hsr.it).

397

398 **Materials availability**

399 This study did not generate new reagents. Nichoids can be obtained through collaboration with
400 Manuela Teresa Raimondi (manuela.raimondi@polimi.it) or purchased from MOAB S.R.L.
401 (<https://moab-research.com/>).

402

403 **Data and code availability**

404 Data used for transcriptomic and IS analyses are accessible at the following repositories:

405 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSE280536>

406 https://github.com/calabrialab/Code_3D_Scaffold

407 Codes used for the generation of results are accessible at the following repositories:

408 <http://www.bioinfotiget.it/gitlab/custom/Midena2024>

409 https://github.com/calabrialab/Code_3D_Scaffold

410

411 **ACKNOWLEDGMENTS**

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416 in Information Technology, Politecnico di Milano. G.F. conducted this study partially fulfilling his
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423 Stem Cell Foundation Robertson Investigator.

424

425 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS**

426 F.M. planned and performed experiments, analyzed, and interpreted the data; L.A. performed and
427 analyzed experiments; C.C. and L.C. produced nichoids and E.J. performed immunofluorescence
428 analyses on them, supervised by M.T.R., G.C., and R.O.; M.B., F.G., and T.T. performed
429 bioinformatics analysis and interpreted computational data, supervised by I.M. and E.M.; E.C. and

430 K.G. provided help with animal experiments; F.B. and S.A. performed VCN and IS analyses,
431 supervised by E.M.; R.V. performed comet assay and helped with several experiments; L.d.V.
432 performed proliferation analyses over time and discussed the data; D.B. and M.F. helped setting up
433 alternative 3D cultures and performed immunofluorescence analyses on them, supervised by C.S.
434 and A.B.; E.Z. helped with LV experiments, supervised by B.G. and M.R.; F.Fe. and F.Fr. provided
435 samples from WAS patients, supervised by A.A.; G.F. performed initial experiments on 3D culture;
436 C.B. and F.C. supervised and performed statistical analyses; M.F. helped with editing experiments,
437 supervised by S.F. and L.N.; S.F., B.G., C.S., A.B., L.N., A.A., E.M., and M.T.R. provided intellectual
438 input and critical discussion. R.D.M. conceived the study, coordinated, interpreted the data, secured
439 funding, and supervised the research. F.M. and R.D.M. wrote the manuscript with inputs from all the
440 authors.

441

442 **DECLARATION OF INTERESTS**

443 F.M., L.d.V., S.F., L.N., and R.D.M. are inventors of patents on applications of gene editing in HSPCs
444 owned and managed by the San Raffaele Scientific Institute and the Telethon Foundation. M.T.R.,
445 G.C., and R.O. are inventors of patents on the nichoid culture substrate and co-founders and quota
446 holders of MOAB S.R.L. All other authors declare no conflict of interest.

447

448 **SUPPLEMENTAL INFORMATION**

449 Document S1. Figure S1-7, related to Figure 1-5.

450 Table S1. Excel file containing cell numbers and cell viability across donors and experiments, related
451 to Figure 1-5 and STAR METHODS.

452 Table S2. Excel file containing additional information on the RNA sequencing analysis (all pages
453 refer to 3D vs. 2D comparisons), related to Figure 2 and STAR METHODS.

454 Table S3. Excel file containing additional information on clonal tracking analysis, related to Figure 4,
455 Figure 5, and STAR METHODS.

456 **Figure 1. Nichoids improve the functionality of *ex vivo* cultured HSPCs.**

457 (A) Schematic representation with highlight of a single elementary unit (top) and scanning electron
458 microscopy images (bottom) of the nichoid culture substrate. Scale bars: 30/90 μm .

459 (B) Experimental workflow. Human CB-derived HSPCs were seeded on 2D or on nichoids
460 immediately after thawing and collected for downstream analyses on days 3 and 7.

461 (C) Percentage of phenotypically defined HSPC subsets (n=9,9,10,10).

462 (D) Number of erythroid, myeloid, and mixed colonies generated in the CFU-C assay (n=6). Wilcoxon
463 test.

464 (E,F) Number of lineages (E) and cells (F) per colony generated by HSC-enriched single cells. More
465 than 250 colonies were analyzed for each condition. Median \pm 95% CI. Mann-Whitney test.

466 (G-I) Percentage of human CD45+ (hCD45+) cells measured in the PB (G) over time, and BM (H)
467 and SP (I) at the endpoint (n=5). Mann-Whitney test (calculated at the last time point for PB).

468 (J) Number of erythroid, myeloid, and mixed colonies generated by BM-derived CD34+ cells purified
469 from mice in (H) (n=5). Mann-Whitney test.

470 Unless otherwise specified, Mean \pm SEM. *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01.

471 See also Figure S1 and Table S1.

472 **Figure 2. Nichoids profoundly rewire *ex vivo* manipulated HSPCs.**

473 (A) Differentially modulated gene categories from GSEA of 3D- vs. 2D-cultured HSPCs. Color
474 gradient reflects the normalized enrichment score (NES); grey boxes indicate non-significant
475 modulation ($p_{\text{adjust}} > 0.05$).

476 (B) Average gene expression (Z-score) for the indicated genes. Differentially expressed genes (FDR
477 < 0.05) are represented with symbols of larger size.

478 (C) Representative plot (left) and MFI (Median Fluorescence Intensity) (right) of CellTrace dye
479 dilution in HSPCs on day 7 ($n=6$). Wilcoxon test.

480 (D) MFI of ROS measured by CellROX staining in HSPCs on day 7 ($n=6$). Wilcoxon test.

481 (E) MFI of 8-oxo-dG in HSPCs on day 7 ($n=6$). Wilcoxon test.

482 (F) Quantification of single-strand and double-strand breaks by alkaline comet assay; each dot
483 represents a single cell (more than 200 cells were analyzed for each condition). Median \pm 95% CI.
484 Mann-Whitney test.

485 (G) Percentage of phospho-p38 (p-p38)-positive HSPCs on day 7 ($n=6$). Wilcoxon test.

486 (H) Representative 3D renderings of HSPCs on day 7 of 2D or 3D culture, obtained from
487 immunofluorescence z-stack confocal imaging. Scale bars: 10 μm .

488 (I,J) Quantification of (I) volume and (J) squashing morphological parameters on day 7; each dot
489 represents a single cell or nucleus (more than 250 cells were analyzed for each condition). Median.
490 Mann-Whitney test.

491 (K) Representative immunofluorescence showing tubulin spatial organization in HSPCs on day 7.
492 Scale bars: 10 μm .

493 (L,M) Representative immunofluorescence (L) and quantification (M) of tubulin score measured
494 along cell diameter in HSPCs on day 7 (more than 100 cells were analyzed for each condition).
495 Median Value. Mann-Whitney test. Scale bars: 5 μm .

496 Unless otherwise specified, Mean \pm SEM. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; **** $p < 0.0001$.

497 See also Figure S2 and S3 and Table S1 and S2.

498 **Figure 3. Nichoids enable efficient gene editing across multiple platforms and superior long-**
499 **term engraftment of HDR-edited HSPCs.**

500 (A) Experimental workflow. Human CB- or mPB-derived HSPCs were seeded on 2D or 3D
501 immediately after thawing and collected on day 3 for nucleofection. Specifically, cells were edited
502 with Cas9/AAV6 alone or in the presence of GSE56 and Ad5-E4orf6/7 editing enhancers to insert a
503 GFP reporter within the *AAVS1* locus. HSPCs from both the 2D and 3D conditions were seeded in
504 2D after nucleofection and collected for downstream analyses on days 4 and 7. Transplantation was
505 performed only for the Cas9/AAV6 plus GSE56 and Ad5-E4orf6/7 editing enhancers treatment using
506 CB-derived HSPCs. After 15 weeks post-injection, CD34+ cells were purified from the BM of the
507 mice and transplanted into secondary recipients.

508 (B) Percentage of edited HSPCs by FACS analysis on day 7 (n=6).

509 (C) Number of erythroid, myeloid, and mixed colonies generated in the CFU-C assay from edited
510 HSPCs seeded on day 4 (n=6). Wilcoxon test.

511 (D,E) Percentage of hCD45+ cells measured in the PB (D) over time and BM (E) at the endpoint of
512 transplanted mice (n=5). Mann-Whitney test (calculated at the last time point for PB).

513 (F) Percentage of GFP+ cells (within hCD45+ cells) in the PB over time from mice in (D) (n=5).

514 (G) Number of erythroid, myeloid, and mixed colonies generated by BM-derived CD34+ cells purified
515 from mice in (E) (n=5). Mann-Whitney test.

516 (H,I), Percentage of hCD45+ cells measured in the PB (H) over time and BM (I) at the endpoint of
517 transplanted secondary recipients (n=8,6). Mann-Whitney test (calculated at the last time point for
518 PB).

519 (J,K) Percentage of GFP+ cells (within hCD45+ cells) in the PB (J) over time and BM (K) from mice
520 in (H,I) (n=8,6). Mann-Whitney test (calculated at the last time point for PB).

521 (L) Experimental workflow. Human mPB-derived HSPCs were seeded on 2D or 3D immediately after
522 thawing and collected on day 3 for nucleofection. Specifically, cells were edited with BE or PE to
523 disrupt the *B2M* gene. HSPCs from both the 2D and 3D conditions were seeded in 2D after
524 nucleofection and collected for downstream analyses on days 4 and 7.

525 (M) Percentage of edited HSPCs by FACS analysis on day 7 (n=6).

526 (N) Number of erythroid, myeloid, and mixed colonies generated in the CFU-C assay from edited
527 HSPCs seeded on day 4 (n=6). Wilcoxon test.

528 Mean \pm SEM. *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01; ***p < 0.001.

529 See also Figure S4 and S5 and Table S1.

530 **Figure 4. Nichoids improve the engraftment and clonal output of HSPCs upon gene addition.**
531 (A) Experimental workflow. Human mPB-derived HSPCs were seeded on 2D or 3D immediately after
532 thawing and transduced on day 1 with a GFP-expressing LV vector in the presence of PGE2 alone
533 or in combination with CsH. Specifically, transduction was performed directly on the scaffolds at MOI
534 100 for PGE2 alone and MOI 30 with CsH. After 14h from transduction (day 2), HSPCs from both
535 the 2D and 3D conditions were collected for downstream analyses on day 2, and seeded in 2D for
536 VCN analyses on day 10. Transplantation was performed only for the CsH condition.
537 (B) Percentage of GFP+ HSPCs by FACS analysis on day 10 (n=6). Wilcoxon test.
538 (C) Number of erythroid, myeloid, and mixed colonies generated in the CFU-C assay from
539 transduced HSPCs seeded on day 2 (n=6). Wilcoxon test.
540 (D,E) Percentage of hCD45+ cells measured in the PB (D) over time and BM (E) at the endpoint of
541 transplanted mice (n=7). Mann-Whitney test (calculated at the last time point for PB).
542 (F) Percentage of GFP+ cells (within hCD45+ cells) in the PB over time from mice in (D) (n=7).
543 (G) Number of erythroid, myeloid, and mixed colonies generated by BM-derived CD34+ cells purified
544 from mice in (E) (n=7). Mann-Whitney test.
545 (H) Representative plots of tracked ISs and their relative abundance over time from mice of the 2D
546 (top, mouse A4) and 3D (bottom, mouse B12) conditions. Each colored bar univocally identifies an
547 IS with >1% representation in at least one time point, with its abundance proportional to the height
548 of the bar; a colored ribbon connects two neighboring time points for each recaptured clone. The
549 total number of unique ISs is reported on each bar.
550 (I,J) Estimated clonal population size (I) and diversity measured by Shannon index (J) normalized
551 on VCN from IS analyses. Mann-Whitney test.
552 (K) Representative plots of CIS from mice of the 2D (left, mouse A4) and 3D (right, mouse B12)
553 conditions. Each dot represents a gene, labeled with the corresponding color if observed as
554 significant. The dashed line is the alpha value 0.05. Grubbs test.
555 Mean \pm SEM. *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01; ***p < 0.001.
556 See also Figure S6 and Table S1 and S3.

557 **Figure 5. Nichoids improve the engraftment and clonal complexity of gene-corrected HSPCs**
558 **in Wiskott-Aldrich Syndrome.**

559 (A) Experimental workflow. mPB-derived HSPCs from WAS patients were seeded on 2D (upon
560 coating with retronectin) or 3D (without retronectin coating) immediately after thawing and
561 transduced directly on the scaffolds with two hits of WASP-expressing LV on days 1 and 2 at MOI
562 100. After 14h from the second round of transduction (day 3), HSPCs from both the 2D and 3D
563 conditions were collected for downstream analyses on day 3, and seeded in 2D for VCN analyses
564 on day 10. Three independent technical replicates were performed for each donor (different symbols
565 identify the two WAS patients).

566 (B) Number of erythroid, myeloid, and mixed colonies generated in the CFU-C assay from
567 transduced HSPCs seeded on day 3 (n=6).

568 (C-E) Percentage of hCD45+ cells measured in the PB (C) over time, and BM (D) and SP (E) at the
569 endpoint (n=5). Random-intercept linear mixed-effects (LME) model.

570 (F) Representative plots of tracked ISs and their relative abundance over time from mice of the 2D
571 (left, mouse A4) and 3D (right, mouse B6) conditions. Each colored bar univocally identifies an IS
572 with >1% representation in at least one time point, with its abundance proportional to the height of
573 the bar; a colored ribbon connects two neighboring time points for each recaptured clone. The total
574 number of unique ISs is reported on each bar.

575 (G,H) Estimated clonal population size (G) and diversity measured by Shannon index (H) normalized
576 on VCN from IS analyses. Random-intercept LME model.

577 (I), Representative plots of CIS from mice of the 2D (left, mouse A4) and 3D (right, mouse B6)
578 conditions. Each dot represents a gene, labeled with the corresponding color if observed as
579 significant. The dashed line is the alpha value 0.05. Grubbs test.

580 Mean \pm SEM. **p < 0.01; ***p < 0.001.

581 See also Figure S7 and Table S1 and S3.

REAGENT or RESOURCE	SOURCE	IDENTIFIER
Antibodies		
Anti-8-oxo-2'-deoxyguanosine	Trevigen	Cat#4354-MC-050; RRID: AB_1857195
Anti-alpha Tubulin antibody - Loading Control	Abcam	Cat#ab4074; RRID: AB_2288001
Anti-human CD11b PE (Clone M1/70)	BioLegend	Cat#101207; RRID: AB_312790
Anti-human CD13 BV421 (Clone WM15)	BD Biosciences	Cat#562596; RRID: AB_2737672
Anti-human CD133/1 PE-Vio 770 (Clone AC133)	Miltenyi Biotec	Cat#130-113-110; RRID: AB_2725939
Anti-human CD14 APC-Cy7 (Clone M5E2)	BioLegend	Cat#301820; RRID: AB_493695
Anti-human CD15 BV510 (Clone W6D3)	BioLegend	Cat#323028; RRID: AB_2563400
Anti-human CD19 BV510 (Clone HIB19)	BioLegend	Cat#302242; RRID: AB_2561668
Anti-human CD235a (GlyA) APC (Clone GA-R2 (HIR2))	BD Biosciences	Cat#551336; RRID: AB_398499
Anti-human CD3 PE (Clone OKT3)	BioLegend	Cat#317308; RRID: AB_571913
Anti-human CD33 BV421 (Clone WM53)	BD Biosciences	Cat#562854; RRID: AB_2737405
Anti-human CD33 PE-Cy7 (Clone P67.6)	BD Biosciences	Cat#333952; RRID: AB_2713932
Anti-human CD34 PE (Clone AC136)	Miltenyi Biotec	Cat#130-113-179; RRID: AB_2726006
Anti-human CD34 PE-Cy7 (Clone 8G12)	BD Biosciences	Cat#348811; RRID: AB_2868855
Anti-human CD38 PerCP-Cy5.5 (Clone HB-7)	BioLegend	Cat#356614; RRID: AB_2562183
Anti-human CD41 PE-Cy5 (Clone HIP8)	BioLegend	Cat#303708; RRID: AB_314378
Anti-human CD45 APC-eFluor 780 (Clone HI30)	Invitrogen	Cat#47-0459-42; RRID: AB_1944368
Anti-human CD45 PE-Cy7 (Clone HI30)	BioLegend	Cat#304016; RRID: AB_314404
Anti-human CD45Ra Alexa Fluor 700 (Clone HI100)	BioLegend	Cat#304120; RRID: AB_493763
Anti-human CD56 Pacific Blue (Clone MEM-188)	BioLegend	Cat#304629; RRID: AB_2282499
Anti-human CD8 PE-Cy7 (Clone RPA-T8)	BD Biosciences	Cat#557746; RRID: AB_396852
Anti-human CD90 APC (Clone 5E10)	BD Biosciences	Cat#559869; RRID: AB_398677
Anti-human FCR Blocking	Miltenyi Biotec	Cat#130059901; RRID: AB_2892112
Anti-human p38-MAPK pThr180/pTyr182	Cell Signalling	Cat#9211; RRID: AB_331641
Donkey anti-mouse IgG (H+L) Secondary Antibody, Alexa Fluor 488	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat#A-21202; RRID: AB_141607
Donkey anti-mouse IgG (H+L) Secondary Antibody, Alexa Fluor 647	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat#A-31571; RRID: AB_162542
Donkey anti-rabbit IgG (H+L) Secondary Antibody, Alexa Fluor 568	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat#A-10042; RRID: AB_2534017
Mouse anti-human Phospho-Histone H2A.X (Ser139) (Clone JBW301)	Merck Millipore	Cat#05-636; RRID: AB_309864
Purified Rat anti-mouse CD16/CD32 (Clone 2.4G2)	BD Biosciences	Cat#553141; RRID: AB_394656
Rabbit anti-human phospho-RPA32 (S33)	Bethyl Laboratories	Cat#A300-246A; RRID: AB_2180847
Biological samples		
Umbilical cord blood	San Raffaele Hospital	N/A
Leukapheresis from WAS patients	San Raffaele Hospital	N/A
Mobilized peripheral blood	Mobilized Leukopak (AICells)	N/A

Chemicals, peptides, and recombinant proteins		
16,16-Dimethyl Prostaglandin E2	Cayman Chemical	Cat#14750
7-AAD Viability Staining solution	Biolegend	Cat#420403
ABE8.20-m	Fiumara et al.	N/A
Alt-R CRISPR-Cas9 Negative Control crRNA #1	Integrated DNA Technologies	Cat#1072544
Cas9 enhancing	Integrated DNA Technologies	Cat#1075916
CellROX™ Deep Red Reagent	Thermo Fisher	Cat#C10422
CometAssay LMAgarose	R&D Systems	Cat#4250-050-02
Corning® Collagen I	Sigma-Aldrich	Cat#CLS354236-1EA
CometAssay Lysis Solution	R&D Systems	Cat#4250-050-01
DAPI	Sigma-Aldrich	Cat#D9542
Erythropoietin (EPO, Eprex)	Janssen-Cilag	N/A
gRNA AAVS1	Schiroli et al.	N/A
gRNA B2M exon 1	Fiumara et al.	N/A
GSE56 and Ad5-E4orf6/7	Ferrari et al.	N/A
Hoechst 3342 Fluorescent Stain	Thermo Fisher	Cat#62249
Human GM-CSF	Miltenyi Biotec	Cat#130-093-862
Human IL-11	Miltenyi Biotec	Cat#130-103-439
Human IL-2	Miltenyi Biotec	Cat#130097743
Human IL-3 recombinant protein	Peprtech	Cat#200-03
Human IL-7	Miltenyi Biotec	Cat#130-095-363
Human Low-Density Lipoproteins (LDL)	Stem Cell Technologies	Cat#02698
Intracellular Staining Permeabilization Wash Buffer	Biolegend	Cat#421002
Liberase™	Sigma-Aldrich	Cat#5401119001
nicking gRNA 5 B2M exon 1	Fiumara et al.	N/A
Pacific Blue Annexin V	Biolegend	Cat#640918
Paraformaldehyde solution 4% in PBS	Santa Cruz Biotechnology	Cat#SC-281692
PE3max	Fiumara et al.	N/A
pegRNA 5 B2M exon 1	Fiumara et al.	N/A
Poly-L-lysine solution	Sigma-Aldrich	Cat#P8920
Recombinant human Flt3-Ligand	Peprtech	Cat#300-19
Recombinant human IL6	Peprtech	Cat#200-06
Recombinant human stem cell factor (SCF)	Peprtech	Cat#300-07
Recombinant human thrombopoietin (TPO)	Peprtech	Cat#300-18
SpCas9 Nuclease	Aldevron	Cat#9212
StemRegenin 1 (SR1)	Biovision	Cat#1967
UM171	STEMCell Technologies	Cat#72914
Critical commercial assays		
CellTrace™ Violet Cell Proliferation Kit	Thermo Scientific	Cat# C34557
Click-iT EdU Pacific Blue Flow cytometry assay kit	Thermo Fisher	Cat#C10418
ddPCR Supermix for Probes (No dUTP)	BioRad	Cat #1863024
ddPCR™ Copy Number Assay: TTC5, Human, Homo sapiens	BioRad	Cat# 12017424
GoTaq Flexi DNA Polymerase	Promega Corporation	Cat#M8295
P3 Primary Cell 4D-Nucleofector X Kit S	Lonza	Cat#V4XP-3032
QIAamp DNA Micro Kit	QIAGEN	Cat#56304
QIAamp DNA Mini Kit	QIAGEN	Cat#51304

QX200™ ddPCR™ EvaGreen Supermix	BioRad	Cat#1864034
RNase-free DNase Set	QIAGEN	Cat#79254
RNeasy Plus Micro Kit	QIAGEN	Cat#74034
T7 endonuclease 1	New England Biolabs	Cat#M0302L
Deposited data		
Integration site analysis	This paper	https://github.com/calabrialab/Code_3D_Scaffold
RNA sequencing	This paper	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSE280536
Experimental models: Cell lines		
Human cord blood CD34+ Stem/Progenitor cells	Lonza	Cat#2C-101
Experimental models: Organisms/strains		
NOD.CG- Prkdc ^{scid} Il2rg ^{tm1Wjl} /SzJ (NSG) <i>Mus Musculus</i>	Charles River Laboratories (IACUC: #1385)	RRID: IMSR_JAX:005557
Oligonucleotides		
See METHOD DETAIL	This paper	N/A
Recombinant DNA		
AAV6.GFP	Schirotti et al.	N/A
LV.GFP	Zonari et al.	N/A
LV.WAS	Ferrua et al.	N/A
Software and algorithms		
BD FACSDiva software	BD Biosciences	https://www.bdbiosciences.com/en-us/products/software/instrument-software/bd-facsddiva-software
CaspLab	CaspLab	https://sourceforge.net/projects/casp/
FlowJo	FlowJo	https://www.flowjo.com/
ImageJ (v2.9)	NIH	https://imagej.nih.gov/ij/
LAS X Leica Software	Leica Microsystems	https://www.leica-microsystems.com/it/prodotti/software-per-microscopi/p/leica-las-x-ls/
Prism software (v10)	GraphPad Prism	https://www.graphpad.com/
QuantaSoft (v1.7)	Biorad	https://www.bio-rad.com/
R statistical software	R Project	https://www.r-project.org/
Vision 4D arivis pro	ZEISS	https://kb.arivis.com/vision4d-arivis-pro
Other		
Nichoids	Politecnico di Milano	N/A
Spongostan	Ferrosan Medical Devices	CAT# MS0005

584

585 **EXPERIMENTAL MODEL AND STUDY PARTICIPANTS DETAILS**586 **Mice**

587 NOD-SCID-IL2rg^{-/-} (NSG) female mice were purchased from Charles River Laboratories and
588 maintained in specific pathogen-free conditions. The procedures involving animals were designed
589 and performed with the approval of the Animal Care and Use Committee of the San Raffaele Hospital
590 and communicated to the Ministry of Health and local authorities according to Italian law (IACUC

591 #1385). Mice sample size was determined in accordance with ethical regulations and the 3Rs
592 principles. Mice were randomly assigned to each experimental group.

593

594 **Primary stem cell cultures**

595 Cord blood-derived CD34+ HSPCs: Cells were either freshly purified from human CB after
596 obtaining informed consent and upon approval by the San Raffaele Hospital ethical committee or
597 purchased frozen from Lonza or StemExpress. HSPCs were cultured in serum-free StemSpan
598 SFEM medium (StemCell Technologies) supplemented with 2mM L-glutamine and Penicillin-
599 Streptomycin (100IU/ml penicillin, 100mg/ml streptomycin), 1µM SR-1 (Biovision), 50nM UM171
600 (STEMCell Technologies), and recombinant human cytokines (100ng/ml SCF, 100ng/ml FLT3-L,
601 20ng/ml TPO, and 20ng/ml IL-6; Peprotech). 10µM 16,16-Dimethyl Prostaglandin E2 (Cayman) was
602 added only at thawing.

603 Mobilized peripheral blood-derived CD34+ HSPCs: Cells were purified in-house with the
604 CliniMACS CD34 Reagent System (Miltenyi Biotec) from Mobilized Leukopak (AllCells, mobilized
605 with G-CSF or G-CSF+Plerixafor) according to the TIGET-HPCT protocol approved by OSR Ethical
606 Committee and following the manufacturer's instructions. HSPCs were cultured in serum-free
607 StemSpan SFEM medium (StemCell Technologies) supplemented with 2mM L-glutamine and
608 Penicillin-Streptomycin (100IU/ml penicillin, 100mg/ml streptomycin), 1µM SR-1(Biovision), 35nM
609 UM17 (STEMCell Technologies), and recombinant human cytokines (300ng/ml SCF, 300ng/ml
610 FLT3-L, and 100ng/ml TPO; Peprotech). 10µM 16,16-Dimethyl Prostaglandin E2 (Cayman) was
611 added only at thawing, only for GE strategies.

612 Wiskott-Aldrich Syndrome-derived CD34+ HSPCs: Cells were purified with human CD34
613 MicroBead Kit (Miltenyi Biotec) from excess material obtained from G-CSF+Plerixafor leukapheresis
614 from patients undergoing gene therapy in the Pediatric immunohematology unit in the San Raffaele
615 Hospital after obtaining informed consent and upon approval by the San Raffaele Hospital ethical
616 committee (protocol TIGET-09). HSPCs were cultured in SCGM medium (CellGenix/Sartorius)
617 supplemented with Penicillin-Streptomycin (100IU/ml penicillin, 100mg/ml streptomycin) and
618 recombinant human cytokines (100ng/ml TPO, 60ng/ml IL3, 300ng/ml SCF, and 300ng/ml FLT3-L;
619 CellGenix/Sartorius). Only for the 2D condition, coating with retronectin (Takara) was performed
620 according to the manufacturer's instructions. GMP-grade reagents were provided by Marina
621 Radrizzani's group.

622 Cell seeding on nichoids: In this study, 1-5×10⁵ cells were seeded in a single nichoid in the current
623 configuration fabricated on a 12 mm slide. To avoid over-confluency, multiple nichoids per donor
624 were used when requiring a larger number of cells. Specifically, 1-5×10⁵ cells were resuspended in
625 100µl of fresh media upon thawing and placed directly on top of the nichoid without directly touching
626 the scaffold. Cells were left seeding for 30-45 min and then topped up with 400µl of culture media.

627 Cell seeding on spongostan scaffolds: spongostan (Ferrosan Medical Devices) was obtained in
628 sterile single cubes of 1×1×1cm and then cut into cylinders of 3.5mm in height and 4mm in diameter,
629 as previously described⁷⁰. Specifically, 2×10⁵ cells were resuspended in 20µl of fresh media upon
630 thawing and placed directly on top of the scaffold positioned in the bottom of a 1.5ml tube. Cells
631 were left seeding for 2h to allow complete absorption of the medium and cell infiltration, and then
632 topped up with 500µl of culture media. The tube containing the scaffold was subsequently placed in
633 the incubator with the cap left open to allow adequate gas exchange, while sterility was maintained
634 by covering the opening with a sterile 0.45µm filter.

635 Cell seeding on spheroids: 300µl of collagen solution was prepared on ice with 205µl of culture
636 media, 9µl of 10X PBS, 2µl of 1M NaOH, and 84µl of rat tail collagen I (Corning) and used
637 immediately after preparation, as previously described⁶⁹. Specifically, 3×10⁵ cells were resuspended
638 in 30µl of collagen solution, and 5µl of cell suspension were spotted as hanging drops (6 per donor)
639 on the lid of a Petri dish. After 30 min of incubation to promote collagen polymerization, spheroids
640 were transferred to a cell culture plate with 2ml of culture media.

641 Cell recovery from nichoids and spongostan scaffolds: Briefly, culture medium was gently
642 removed, and scaffolds were covered with 500µl citrate solution (0.015M sodium citrate, 0.135M KCl
643 in sterile H₂O). Cells were incubated for 15 min in the incubator and then recovered by gently
644 pipetting close to the scaffold. After a second quick wash with citrate solution, the cellular suspension
645 was diluted in DPBS, pelleted, and resuspended in the appropriate volume of culture medium.

646 Cell recovery from spheroids: Spheroids were collected and digested in 90µl of Liberase solution
647 (0.3mg/mL in FBS, Sigma-Aldrich) in a thermomixer at 37°C for 10 min at 900rpm. The cellular
648 suspension was diluted in DPBS, pelleted, and resuspended in the appropriate volume of culture
649 medium.

650 All cells were cultured in a 5% CO₂ humidified atmosphere at 37°C. Equal numbers of cells were
651 used to perform head-to-head comparisons between 2D- and 3D-cultured HSPCs, counted by
652 Trypan Blue exclusion. Detailed cell numbers and cell viability across donors and experiments are
653 reported in Table S1.

654

655 **METHOD DETAILS**

656 **Nichoids fabrication**

657 Nichoids were provided by Manuela Teresa Raimondi's group (Politecnico di Milano) and
658 fabricated as described in previous works¹⁰⁰ using two-photon polymerization of the SZ2080
659 biocompatible resin on a circular borosilicate glass coverslip (170µm in thickness and 12mm in
660 diameter, Bio-Optica). The resin's two-photon absorption cross-section was enhanced by adding the
661 commercial photoinitiator, Irgacure-369. SZ2080 was chosen for its mechanical properties, low
662 cytotoxicity, and low autofluorescence¹⁰¹. A cavity-dumped femtosecond laser with a 1030nm
663 wavelength, pulse duration under 400fs, and 1MHz repetition rate was focused into the

664 photosensitive material through a high-magnification oil-immersion microscope objective (100X, 1.4
665 numerical aperture, Plan-Apochromat, Carl Zeiss). Three fast linear stages (two horizontal and one
666 vertical, ANT130, Aerotech) were used to move the sample across the laser beam, enabling
667 continuous polymerization over the entire substrate. A translation velocity of 3mm/s was set.

668 The nichoid structure comprised two perpendicular sets of six parallel lines, 90×90µm in
669 transverse dimensions, and consisted of a lattice of interconnected lines, with a graded spacing
670 between 10 and 30µm transversely and a uniform spacing of 15µm vertically. 30µm tall columns
671 were placed at each line crossing to provide structural support. Nichoids were arranged in 5x5-unit
672 blocks, sharing side walls, and the entire glass substrate was covered by these blocks, separated
673 by 30µm corridors. Following the fabrication process, samples underwent development in a 50%
674 (v/v) 2-pentanone and 50% (v/v) isopropyl alcohol solution to eliminate unirradiated photoresist,
675 washed with clean isopropyl alcohol, and dried with nitrogen.

676 To ensure sterility before cell culture, nichoids were covered with 70% EtOH solution for at least
677 3 hours, washed three times with ddH₂O, and exposed to UV-C irradiation for at least 30 min.

678 Images of the nichoid culture substrate by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Phenom Pro,
679 Phenom-World) were provided by Politecnico di Milano.

680

681 **Genetic engineering**

682 The initial number of cells subject to genetic engineering was equal for the 2D and 3D conditions
683 but variable between experiments, depending on the number of cells required for downstream
684 analyses (Table S1).

685 Cas9/AAV6: After three days of *ex vivo* culture, cells were nucleofected with 2.5-1.25µM of
686 ribonucleoproteins (RNPs) and electroporation enhancer (Integrated DNA Technologies) according
687 to the manufacturer's instructions using P3 Primary Cell 4D-Nucleofector X Kit and program EO-100
688 (Lonza). RNPs were assembled by incubating for 10 min at room temperature at 1:1.5 molar ratio
689 S.p. Cas9 protein (Aldevron) with synthetic gRNAs (Integrated DNA Technologies) targeting the
690 *AAVS1* locus²⁴ (sequence: GTCACCAATCCTGTCCCTAG). Transduction with AAV6 (purchased
691 from AAV vector core, TIGEM) was performed at a dose of 1×10⁴ vg/cell after electroporation. The
692 design of AAV6 donor templates encoding for a PGK.GFP reporter cassette with homologies for the
693 *AAVS1* locus was previously reported²⁴. GSE56-Ad5-E4orf6/7 mRNA was provided by Luigi
694 Naldini's group³⁴. Editing efficiency was assessed by FACS analyses, digital droplet PCR (ddPCR),
695 and T7 endonuclease 1 assay.

696 Base-editing: After three days of *ex vivo* culture, cells were nucleofected with 75pmol of synthetic
697 gRNA (Synthego) targeting the exon 1 of *B2M* (sequence: GAGTAGCGCGAGCACAGCTA) and
698 3.5µg of ABE8.20-m optimized RNA (provided by Luigi Naldini's group)²⁵ according to the
699 manufacturer's instructions using P3 Primary Cell 4D-Nucleofector X Kit and program EO-100

700 (Lonza). Editing efficiency was assessed by FACS analyses using anti-human B2M FITC
701 (BioLegend) and Sanger Sequencing.

702 Prime-editing: After three days of *ex vivo* culture, cells were nucleofected with 186 pmol of *B2M*
703 pegRNA (Integrated DNA Technologies, sequence:
704 mG*mA*mG*UAGCGCGAGCACAGCUAGUUUUAGAGCUAGAAAUAGCAAGUUAAAAUAAGGC
705 UAGUCCGUUAUCAACUUGAAAAAGUGGCACCGAGUCGGUGCUCGGUGGCCUGAGCUGUGC
706 UCGCGCUMU*mU*mU), 75pmol of synthetic gRNA (Synthego) targeting the exon 1 of *B2M*
707 (sequence: AGTGGAGGCGTCGCGCTGGC), and 7.5µg of PEmax optimized mRNA (provided by
708 Luigi Naldini's group)²⁵ according to the manufacturer's instructions using P3 Primary Cell 4D-
709 Nucleofector X Kit and program EO-100 (Lonza). Editing efficiency was assessed by FACS analyses
710 using anti-human B2M FITC (BioLegend) and Sanger Sequencing.

711 For genome editing, 1-7.5×10⁵ cells were generally electroporated in a single 16-well
712 nucleocuvette strip (larger numbers of cells were divided in multiple nucleocuvette wells).

713 Lentiviral gene addition: According to the experimental design described in the main text, cells
714 were transduced for 14h with third-generation self-inactivating lentiviruses encoding for a PGK.GFP
715 reporter cassette³⁷ or WASP under the control of a 1.6 kb reconstituted WAS promoter (two rounds
716 of transduction; GMP-grade vector, provided by Marina Radrizzani's group)⁷³. 10µM 16,16-Dimethyl
717 Prostaglandin E2 (Cayman) was added 2h prior to transduction. 8µM Cyclosporine H (Sigma-
718 Aldrich) was added together with 16,16-Dimethyl Prostaglandin E2 (Cayman). Gene transfer
719 efficiency was assessed by FACS analyses and ddPCR.

720

721 **Functional assays**

722 ***Colony-forming unit cell assay***

723 CFU-C assay was performed by plating 800 or 5000 cells (from *ex vivo* culture or upon isolation
724 from the bone marrow of transplanted mice, respectively) in methylcellulose-based medium
725 (MethoCult H4434, StemCell Technologies) supplemented with Penicillin-Streptomycin (100IU/ml
726 penicillin, 100mg/ml streptomycin). Three technical replicates were performed for each sample, and
727 the mean value was plotted and used for statistical analysis. Two weeks after plating, colonies were
728 counted in a blinded fashion. Erythroid, myeloid, and mixed colonies were identified according to
729 morphological criteria. Representative pictures were acquired with the STEMvision Instrument.

730

731 ***Myeloid-Erythroid-Megakaryocyte (MEM) single-cell differentiation assay***

732 CD34+CD133+CD45RA-CD90+ population (negative to ZombieAqua viable dye) was sorted as
733 single cells (1 cell/well) and seeded in U-bottom 96-well filled with 100 µl/well MEM cytokine
734 medium⁵²: StemPro medium with nutrients supplement (Life Technologies) supplemented with 2mM
735 L-glutamine and Penicillin-Streptomycin (100IU/ml penicillin, 100mg/ml streptomycin), recombinant
736 human cytokines (100ng/ml SCF, 20ng/ml Flt3-L, 100ng/ml TPO, 50ng/ml IL-6, 10ng/ml IL-3,

737 50ng/ml IL-11, 20ng/ml GM-CSF, 10ng/ml IL-2, 20ng/ml IL-7; Miltenyi Biotec), 3UI/ml erythropoietin
738 (Eprex, Janssen-Cilag), and 50ng/ml h-LDL (Stem Cell Technologies). Cell sorting was performed
739 with BD FACSAria Fusion (BD Biosciences); cells were sorted with a 100µm nozzle.

740

741 ***Xenotransplantation studies***

742 Xenotransplantation studies were performed on 6/10-weeks-old NSG female mice by intravenous
743 injection after sub-lethal irradiation (150-180 cGy). Up to six different HSPC donors were pooled at
744 thawing, and the resulting pool of cells was split between the 2D and 3D conditions for
745 transplantation, except in the WAS-related experiment, for which the two patients were kept
746 separated. Pooling was performed to reach sufficient numbers of cells for transplantation and to
747 generate a more uniform input population while still preserving a degree of donor-derived diversity,
748 offering a more representative model than single-donor samples. Different pools of donors were
749 used to perform each transplantation experiment presented in the manuscript.

750 The number of cells transplanted into each mouse is reported as follows: 1×10^5 CB-derived
751 CD34+ cells for non-genetically manipulated HSPCs, 5×10^5 CB-derived CD34+ cells for Cas9/AAV6
752 + GSE56 and Ad5-E4orf6/7 edited HSPCs, 4×10^5 mPB-derived CD34+ cells for LV-transduced
753 HSPCs, and $4\text{-}5 \times 10^5$ cells (depending on the donor) for WAS patient-derived HSPCs.

754 For secondary transplantation of Cas9/AAV6 + GSE56 and Ad5-E4orf6/7 edited HSPCs, CD34+
755 cells purified from the BM of primary recipients were pooled according to the experimental group,
756 and 1×10^6 cells were then injected intravenously into each mouse.

757 Human engraftment and the presence of engineered cells were monitored through FACS
758 analyses by serial collection of blood from the mouse tail, and bone marrow and spleen (at endpoint).

759

760 **Molecular analyses**

761 ***Digital droplet PCR***

762 Genomic DNA was isolated with QIAamp DNA Mini or Micro Kit (QIAGEN), and ddPCR was
763 performed using the QX200 Droplet Digital PCR System (Biorad) according to the manufacturer's
764 instructions.

765 For HDR-editing with Cas9/AAV6, 10ng of genomic DNA was analyzed with ddPCR Supermix for
766 Probes (BioRad). Primers and probes were designed between the HDR donor template sequence
767 and the 3' integration junction on the target AAVS1 locus (FW: GATTGGGAAGACAATAGCAG;
768 REV: TCTTGGGAAGTGTAAGGAAG; probe: CCAGATAAGGAATCTGCCTA). The TTC5 gene was
769 used as the control sequence, and the respective primers and probes were purchased in the
770 PrimePCR ddPCR Copy Number Assay: TTC5, Human (BioRad). The different probes were
771 conjugated with FAM (target) and HEX (TTC5 reference) fluorophores. Thermal conditions for
772 annealing and extension were adjusted as follows: 95°C x 10 min; 94°C x 30 sec, 55°C x 1 min,
773 72°C x 2 min (40 cycles); 98°C x 10 min.

774 For VCN analyses, 10ng of genomic DNA was analyzed with EvaGreen Supermix (BioRad).
775 Primers were designed to amplify only integrated LV (FW: TCACTCCCAACGAAGACAAGATC;
776 REV: GAGTCCTGCGTCGAGAGAG), normalized using the *TERT* (FW:
777 GGCACACGTGGCTTTTCG; REV: GGTGAACCTCGTAAGTTTATGCAA) gene as a control
778 sequence, as previously reported³⁵. Thermal conditions for annealing and extension were adjusted
779 as follows: 95°C x 5 min; 95°C x 30 sec, 63°C x 1 min (40 cycles); 4°C x 5 min; 90°C x 5 min.

780

781 ***T7 endonuclease 1 assay***

782 Genomic DNA from Cas9/AAV6-edited cells purified for ddPCR analysis was used to measure
783 non-homologous end joining (NHEJ) efficiency through the mismatch-sensitive T7 endonuclease 1
784 (New England Biolabs) assay by PCR-based amplification of the targeted locus, followed by
785 digestion, as previously reported²⁴ and according to the manufacturer's instructions. PCR
786 amplification was performed with GoTaq Flexi DNA Polymerase (Promega Corporation) using
787 primers specific for *AAVS1* (FW: CTTCAGGACAGCATGTTTGC, REV:
788 ACAGGAGGTGGGGTTAGAC) with thermal conditions for annealing and extension adjusted as
789 follows: 95°C x 10 min; 95°C x 30 sec, 61°C x 30 sec, 72°C x 90 sec (40 cycles); 72°C x 10 min;
790 90°C x 5 min. PCR product was then denatured and annealed as follows: 95°C x 10 min; 95°C to
791 85°C x -2°C/sec; 85°C to 25°C x -0.1°C/sec. Samples were then digested according to the
792 manufacturer's instructions. Digested DNA fragments were resolved and quantified by capillary
793 electrophoresis on a 4200 TapeStation System according to the manufacturer's instructions.

794

795 ***Sanger Sequencing***

796 Genomic DNA was isolated with QIAamp DNA Mini or Micro Kit (QIAGEN). 50-100ng of DNA was
797 amplified by PCR using primers for the *B2M* exon 1, as previously reported²⁵ (FW:
798 CGCGTTTAATATAAGTGGAGGC; REV: GGAGAACTTGGAGAAGGGAAGT). Thermal conditions
799 for annealing and extension were adjusted as follows: 95°C x 10 min; 95°C x 30 sec, 59°C x 30 sec,
800 72°C x 30 sec (40 cycles); 72°C x 10 min. Afterward, PCR amplicons were purified using AMPure
801 XP Beads (Beckman Coulter) according to the manufacturer's instructions. 10ng of purified PCR
802 products were sequenced using the REV primer. Sequencing data were analyzed with the online
803 tool EditR.

804

805 ***Flow cytometry***

806 ***Immunophenotypic and apoptosis analysis***

807 For immunophenotypic analyses of *ex vivo* cultured HSPCs, 3-10×10⁴ cells were washed with
808 2% FBS in DPBS and stained with the following fluorescent-labeled antibodies (1:100 dilution, each)
809 for 15 min at 4°C: anti-human CD34 PE (Miltenyi Biotec), anti-human CD133 PE-Vio 770 (Miltenyi
810 Biotec), and anti-human CD90 APC (BD Biosciences). Cells were washed in 2% FBS in DPBS.

811 Where indicated, immunophenotypic staining was combined with Annexin V (BioLegend) and 7-
812 amino-actinomycin D (7-AAD) (BioLegend) viability staining according to the manufacturer's
813 instructions (3 and 1 µl *per* sample, respectively).

814 For immunophenotypic analyses of cells retrieved from *in vivo* organs, blood samples and purified
815 cells were washed with 2% FBS in DPS and incubated with anti-human and anti-mouse FcR Blocking
816 (1:100 and 1:200 dilution, respectively; Miltenyi Biotec) for 10 min at room temperature. Then, cells
817 were stained with combinations of the following fluorescent-labeled antibodies (1:100 dilution, each)
818 for 15 min at 4°C: anti-human CD45 APC-eFluor 780 (Invitrogen), anti-human CD19 BV510 (BD
819 Biosciences), anti-human CD13 BV421 (BD Biosciences), anti-human CD33 PE-Cy7 (BD
820 Biosciences), anti-human CD3 PE (BioLegend), anti-human CD8 APC (BioLegend), and anti-human
821 CD34 PE-Cy7 (BD Biosciences). Cells were washed in 2% FBS in DPBS. 7-AAD was employed as
822 a viability stain.

823 Sample acquisition was performed with FACSCanto II (BD Biosciences). Single-stained and
824 Fluorescence Minus One (FMO) stained cells were used as controls, and SPHERO™ Rainbow
825 Calibration Particles (Spherotech) were used to perform instrument calibration. Data were analyzed
826 using the FlowJo software.

827

828 ***MEM single-cell differentiation assay analysis***

829 All single-cell-derived colonies were stained directly into 96 U-bottom plates. Cells were washed
830 with 100 µl/well 2% FBS in DPBS and then stained with 50 µl/well of the following antibody mix: anti-
831 human CD45-PECy7 (1:300; BioLegend), anti-human CD11b-PE (1:500; BioLegend), anti-human
832 CD41-PECy5 (1:200; BioLegend), anti-human GlyA-APC (1:1000; BD Biosciences), anti-human
833 CD14-APCCy7 (1:500; BioLegend), anti-human CD56-BV421 (1:200; BioLegend), and anti-human
834 CD15-BV510 (1:1000; BioLegend) for 20 min at room temperature and then washed with 100 µl/well
835 2% FBS in DPBS + 2% FBS. Samples acquisition was performed by high-throughput flow cytometry
836 with FACSCanto II (BD Biosciences). Colonies were considered only if composed of ≥ 30 cells.

837

838 ***Proliferation analysis with CellTrace Violet***

839 Immediately after thawing, HSPCs were stained with Cell Trace Violet (Thermo Fisher Scientific)
840 following the manufacturer's instructions. Cells were resuspended in DPBS at a concentration of
841 1×10^6 /ml, and 1 µl of Cell Trace solution was added to each ml of cell suspension for a final
842 concentration of 5 µM. Cells were incubated for 20 min in the incubator at 37°C and then for 5 min
843 with five times the original staining volume of 2% FBS in DPBS. After centrifugation, cells were
844 resuspended in the appropriate culture medium volume. After at least 30 min, samples were acquired
845 with FACSCanto II (BD Biosciences) to check the effectiveness of the staining. Proliferation analyses
846 were subsequently performed on day 7. Data were analyzed using the FlowJo software.

847

848 ***CellROX staining***

849 CellRox (Thermo Fisher Scientific) was pre-diluted in DMSO according to the manufacturer's
850 instructions. 1µM CellROX was directly added to the cell culture (3-10×10⁴ cells). Cells were
851 incubated for 10 and 40 min, respectively, in the incubator at 37°C. After washing in 2% FBS in
852 DPBS, Samples were immediately acquired with FACSCanto II (BD Biosciences). Data were
853 analyzed using the FlowJo software.

854

855 ***8-oxo-2'-deoxyguanosine staining***

856 3-10×10⁴ cells were washed with 2% FBS in DPBS and fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde (Santa
857 Cruz Biotechnology) at room temperature for 15 min. Cells were washed again and denatured with
858 100 µl of HCl (2N) for 20 min at room temperature. After washing with 2% FBS in DPBS, cells were
859 permeabilized with 800µl of 1X Intracellular Staining Permeabilization Wash Buffer (BioLegend) for
860 20 min at room temperature. Then, cells were washed with 2% FBS in DPBS and stained with 8-
861 oxo-2'-deoxyguanosine Antibody (1:250 dilution) (Bio-Techne) at 4°C overnight. After washing with
862 2% FBS in DPBS, samples were stained with anti-mouse secondary antibody Alexa Fluor 488
863 (1:1000 dilution) (Thermo Fisher Scientific) for 45 min at room temperature. Cells were washed with
864 2% FBS in DPBS, and sample acquisition was performed with FACSCanto II (BD Biosciences). Data
865 were analyzed using the FlowJo software.

866

867 ***Phospho-p38 staining***

868 3-10×10⁴ cells were washed with 2% FBS in DPBS, eventually stained with surface markers, and
869 fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde (Santa Cruz Biotechnology) at room temperature for 15 min. Cells
870 were washed again with 2% FBS in DPBS and permeabilized with 100µl of 1X Click-iT saponin-
871 based permeabilization at room temperature for 15 min. Then, cells were stained with phospho-p38
872 MAPK antibody (1:100 dilution) (pThr180/pTyr182; Cell Signalling) at 4°C overnight. After washing
873 with 2% FBS in DPBS, samples were stained with anti-rabbit secondary antibodies (1:1000 dilution)
874 (Alexa Fluor 488 or Alexa Fluor 647; Thermo Fisher Scientific) for 45 min at room temperature. After
875 washing with 2% FBS in DPBS, sample acquisition was performed with FACSCanto II (BD
876 Biosciences), and the collected data were analyzed using the FlowJo software.

877

878 ***Cell cycle analysis***

879 Cell cycle analyses were performed by Click-iT EdU Alexa Fluor PacifiBlue Imaging Kit (Thermo-
880 Fisher Scientific) and Hoechst (Thermo Fisher Scientific) staining. 3-10×10⁴ cells were treated with
881 2µM 5-ethynyl-2'-deoxyuridine (EdU) for 4 hours in culture. Then, cells were washed with 2% FBS
882 in DPBS and fixed with 100µl of Click-iT fixative for 15 min at room temperature. Cells were washed
883 again and permeabilized with 100µl of 1X Click-iT saponin-based permeabilization for 15 min at
884 room temperature. EdU was marked by incubating cells with 500µl of Click-iT Plus reaction cocktail

885 for 30 min at room temperature. Finally, cells were washed and stained with DNA with 2 μ M Hoechst
886 overnight at 4°C. After the incubation, sample acquisition was performed with FACSymphony A5
887 SORP (BD Biosciences). Data were analyzed using the FlowJo software.

888

889 **Immunofluorescence analysis**

890 For the analyses of γ H2AX and pRPA DDR sensors: multitest slides (MP Biomedicals) were
891 treated with Poly-L-lysine solution (Sigma-Aldrich) at 1mg/ml concentration for 20 min at room
892 temperature. After two washes with DPBS solution, approximately 3-10 \times 10⁴ cells were seeded on
893 covers for 20 min and fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde (Santa Cruz Biotechnology) for another 20
894 min. After washing, cells were then permeabilized with 0.3% Triton X-100 for 15 min at room
895 temperature. After blocking with 0.5% BSA and 0.2% fish gelatin in DPBS for 30 min, cells were
896 probed with anti-phospho Histone H2A.X (1:200 dilution; Ser139, clone JBW301; Merk) and
897 phospho-RPA32 (1:200 dilution; S33; Bethyl Laboratories) for 1h at room temperature. After primary
898 antibodies incubation, cells were washed three times with blocking solution and incubated with Alexa
899 488-, 568- and/or 647-labeled secondary antibodies (1:1000 dilution) for 45 min at room temperature
900 (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Nuclear DNA was stained with 0.2mg/ml DAPI (Sigma-Aldrich), and
901 covers were mounted with Aqua-Poly/Mount solution (Polysciences Inc.) on glass slides (Bio-
902 Optica). Fluorescent images were acquired using a Leica SP5 Confocal microscope. Foci
903 quantification was performed with the ImageJ software.

904 For the analysis of HSPC morphology and tubulin distribution: cells were fixed directly on
905 nichoids, spongostan-made scaffolds, spheroids, or coverglasses (Bio-Optica) on day 7 of *ex vivo*
906 culture with 4% paraformaldehyde (Santa Cruz Biotechnology) for 20 min at room temperature. To
907 remove PAF residues and to diminish cell autofluorescence, samples were incubated for 5 min with
908 0.1M glycine solubilized in PBS. Cells were permeabilized with 0.25% Triton-X-100 in PBS solution
909 for 10 min at room temperature. After blocking with 2% BSA in 0.1%Tween20 solution for a few
910 hours (up to 4), cells were incubated overnight and at 4°C, with anti-alpha tubulin primary antibody
911 (1:200 dilution; Abcam) diluted in a 0.1%Tween20 solution. Samples were washed three times in
912 PBS and then incubated with Alexa 488-labeled secondary antibodies (1:1000 dilution, Abcam) for
913 45 min at room temperature. Cell nuclei were labelled with 1 mg/ml Hoechst 33342 (Thermo Fisher
914 Scientific) for 15 min at room temperature. Finally, after washing twice in PBS and once in distilled
915 water, samples were mounted in Mowiol (Sigma-Aldrich). Samples were acquired using a Nikon
916 AR1+ confocal microscope (60X oil immersion objective, 1.4NA 0.13WD, pinhole set to 0.9 Airy
917 Units) or an Olympus fluoVIEW FV3000RS Confocal microscope (60X oil immersion objective,
918 pinhole set to 1 Airy Units). 1024X1024 pixel images were acquired as z-stack images, with a 0.3mm
919 step. Fluorescent images were analyzed with ImageJ and Arivis Vision4D.

920

921 **Comet assay**

922 HSPCs were suspended at 1×10^5 cells/ml in ice-cold DPBS and mixed with molten Comet
923 LMAgarose (Trevigen, MD) at a ratio of 1:10 (v/v) and immediately pipetted onto CometSlides
924 (Trevigen, MD) and placed for 30 min at 4°C. Once solidified, slides were immersed in pre-chilled
925 Lysis Solution (Trevigen, MD) for 1 hour at 4°C. Following lysis, slides were immersed in freshly
926 prepared Alkaline Unwinding Solution pH > 13 (300 mM NaOH, 1mM EDTA) for 1 hour at 4°C and
927 then electrophoresed in Alkaline Electrophoresis Solution pH > 13 (300 mM NaOH, 1mM EDTA) at
928 300 mA for 40 min. Slides were washed twice in ddH₂O and fixed with 70% ethanol for 5 min.
929 Comets were stained with SYBR Safe (Invitrogen) for 30 min at room temperature. All steps were
930 conducted in the dark to prevent additional DNA damage. Comets were analyzed using a Nikon
931 Eclipse E600 microscope and a Nikon-DS-R12 camera. Quantification of the Olive Tail Moment of
932 individual nuclei was performed with the CaspLab software.

933

934 **Transcriptomic analyses**

935 RNA extraction was performed with the RNeasy Plus Micro Kit (QIAGEN) following the
936 manufacturer's instructions. RNA samples were quantified with Qubit RNA HS Assay Kit (Thermo
937 Fischer Scientific) and sequenced in a NovaSeq 2x150 configuration.

938 Raw FASTQ data underwent quality assessment using FastQC. Subsequently, reads were
939 trimmed for adapter sequences and low-quality bases at the 3'-end with TrimGalore (v0.5.0) and
940 aligned to the GRCh38 reference genome using STAR (v2.7.0d). The Gencode primary assembly
941 gene transfer file (GTF) v35 served as a reference for gene annotation. Post-alignment metrics, such
942 as coverage distribution across gene lengths and the percentage of reads mapping to exons, were
943 gathered using Qorts (v1.3.5). Reads were assigned to genes with featureCounts (v1.6.3),
944 considering reads that overlapped exons by at least ten nucleotides (--minOverlap 10) and excluding
945 chimeric reads. Data preprocessing, exploratory analyses, and differential gene expression
946 assessments were conducted using built-in functions from the DESeq2 (v1.30.0) R package. Genes
947 with an adjusted p-value below 0.05 from the differential expression analysis were deemed
948 differentially expressed (Table S2).

949 Pre-ranked gene lists based on log₂ fold change (log₂FC) were utilized for Gene Set Enrichment
950 Analysis (GSEA). These analyses considered various datasets, including Gene Ontology, KEGG
951 Pathway Database, Reactome Pathway Database, and Molecular Signatures Database v7, using
952 built-in functions from the R package clusterProfiler (v.3.8.1). Terms with an adjusted p-value
953 (Benjamini-Hochberg correction) of less than 0.05 were classified as significantly enriched (Table
954 S2).

955

956 **Integration site analyses**

957 ***Retrieval of vector IS***

958 The genomic DNA from mouse-derived samples was extracted with QIAmp DNA Mini or Micro
959 Kit (QIAGEN) and subjected to custom PCR amplification to retrieve vector ISs, the Sonication Linker
960 mediated (SLiM)-PCR^{102,103}. The SLiM-PCR was performed using the NEBNext® Ultra™ II DNA
961 Library Prep Kit (New England Biolabs, ref: E7645) according to the manufacturer's instructions.
962 Briefly, the procedure consists of the following steps: i) fragmentation by sonication of ~30 ng of DNA
963 per sample. ii) splitting of each sample into three replicates. iii) end-repair, adenylation, and ligation
964 of the fragments to a linker cassette (LC) iv) two consecutive rounds of PCR (25 and 10 cycles of
965 amplification, respectively) to amplify vector/cellular-genome junctions by using primers annealing
966 to the vector genome end (Long Terminal Repeats, LTR) and the LC. Between the first and second
967 PCRs, a clean-up and concentration step was performed to prepare the PCR product for the second
968 reaction. The list of primers and sequences used for the SLiM-PCR procedure is reported in Table
969 S3. Primers contain DNA barcodes, which allow univocal barcoding of all the SLiM-PCR replicates,
970 and sequencing adapters for multiplexed paired-end sequencing on Illumina or MGI sequencers.
971 The list of samples with the details on the applied PCR procedure and the number of reads retrieved
972 is reported in Table S3. Two sequencing libraries composed of 267 PCR products were sequenced
973 using the MGI DNBSEQ-G400 platform and yielded a total of $>12.7 \times 10^7$ raw reads.

974

975 ***Identification of vector IS***

976 VISPA2¹⁰⁴ was used for the identification of integration sites (IS) from PCR-amplified samples,
977 which were sequenced using Illumina/MGI paired-end technology. In summary, for each sequencing
978 library generated, we performed quality control filtering on paired-end reads, and barcodes were
979 detected to enable sample demultiplexing. Vector sequences were excised from the reads. The
980 remaining cellular genomic sequences were aligned to the Human reference genome
981 (GRCh37/hg19, February 2019 release). To quantify the number of genomes corresponding to each
982 clone, we employed an estimation strategy based on the count of distinct fragments associated with
983 each IS, utilizing the SonicLength¹⁰⁵ approach. This ensured that IS abundance was proportionate
984 to the initial population of contributing cells, allowing for an estimation of clonal representation in the
985 original sample. The final set of unique IS comprised loci that were precisely mapped and annotated
986 with the closest RefSeq gene.

987 We then used ISAanalytics¹⁰⁶ to integrate the output files of VISPA2 and perform downstream
988 analyses of IS, from quality controls to the analyses of shared IS among samples. A detailed report
989 and code of ISAanalytics are available in the GitHub repository. We initially eliminated the
990 occurrence of identical IS detected across different independent samples, referred to as "collisions,"
991 following a previously established approach⁸. In brief, for the two groups of mice sharing ISs, we
992 attributed the IS to one group if it was first identified in that one or if its relative abundance was at
993 least ten times greater compared to the other group. The detection and resolution of collisions in
994 independent samples were conducted using the ISAanalytics tool. We subsequently carried out

995 quality control of the sequencing data by examining the read count for each PCR sample within each
996 sequencing pool. Samples displaying a raw read count that was significantly under-represented (less
997 than one-third of the average read count of other samples in the pool) were excluded from further
998 analysis. The quality control process involved: i) the exclusion of sequencing samples with raw read
999 counts that were three times lower than the pool's average, and ii) the elimination of potential
1000 contaminations, identified as identical ISs found in separate samples, as previously outlined⁸. For
1001 the analysis of Common Insertion Sites (CIS), we employed the Grubbs test for outlier detection⁷²
1002 (as implemented in ISAnalytics). Specifically, for each mouse, we calculated the targeting frequency
1003 of individual genes based on the number of IS located within the gene body or ± 100 kb and
1004 normalized this by the gene length. After applying a log₂ transformation to the distribution of gene
1005 frequencies, we conducted the Grubbs test to identify genes with targeting frequencies significantly
1006 exceeding the overall average frequency.

1007

1008 **Population size and diversity**

1009 The estimated population size represents the number of transduced engrafting clones and was
1010 calculated as the number of unique IS normalized on the VCN of cells at transplantation (when VCN
1011 >1, to avoid indirect estimation of untransduced clones). Population diversity was calculated using
1012 the Shannon diversity index (H-index). H-index accounts for the number of distinct species (richness)
1013 and their relative abundance with the following formula: $H' = -\sum_{i=1}^R p_i \ln p_i$; where i is an IS, p_i is
1014 the clonal abundance, and R is the set of clones. Several clonal studies have investigated the
1015 heterogeneity and complexity of vector-marked cells across time, tissues, and differentiated
1016 lineages, using IS as a proxy for different species and IS abundance as an indicator of species
1017 prevalence. Richness and evenness were measured over time to assess long-term efficacy
1018 (reflected by the maintenance of a high H-index) or to detect malignant events (indicated by a sharp
1019 decline in the H-index over time). The H-index was calculated using the R package Vegan,
1020 incorporated into ISAnalytics, and normalized on the VCN (when VCN >1) (Table S3).

1021

1022 **QUANTIFICATION AND STATISTICAL ANALYSIS**

1023 Measurements were taken from distinct biological samples, animals, or experiments, and the
1024 sample size (n) is indicated in the figure legends. Distinct biological samples are identified with
1025 different symbols. To adhere to the highest standards of statistical rigor, statistical comparisons were
1026 not performed when $n < 5$ or for *in vitro* experiments of independently processed and transduced cells
1027 purified from the two distinct WAS patients. For paired observations, the Wilcoxon matched-pairs
1028 signed rank test was performed. The Mann-Whitney test was performed to compare two independent
1029 groups. For the *in vivo* experiment of WAS patient-derived cells, random-intercept linear mixed-
1030 effects (LME) models were used to compare biological measurements between 2D and 3D groups,
1031 either at a fixed time point within an organ or within specific cell types, depending on the context, to

1032 account for dependency among observations due to shared donors. A random effect for donor ID
1033 was specified in the model. Standard transformations (e.g., logarithmic, square root, cubic root, and
1034 ordered quantile normalization) were applied to the outcome variables to satisfy model assumptions.
1035 The Grubbs test was performed on CIS results from IS analyses. All tests were performed with two-
1036 tailed statistics. Data were analyzed using the Prism software (GraphPad Software Inc.) and R
1037 statistical software. p values <0.05 were considered significant (*, $p<0.05$; **, $p<0.01$; ***, $p<0.001$;
1038 ****, $p<0.0001$).

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